

Quantum-Classical Simulations Reveal the Photoisomerization Mechanism of a Prototypical First-Generation Molecular Motor

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Light-driven molecular rotary motors convert the energy of absorbed light into unidirectional rotational motion and are key components in the design of molecular machines. The archetypal class of light-driven rotary motors is chiral overcrowded alkenes, where the rotational movement is achieved through consecutive cis-trans photoisomerization reactions and thermal helix inversion steps. While the thermal steps have been rather well understood by now, our understanding of the photoisomerization reactions of overcrowded alkene-based motors still misses key points that would explain the striking differences in operation efficiency of the known systems. Here, we employ quantum-chemical calculations and nonadiabatic molecular dynamics simulations to investigate the excited-state decay and

photoisomerization mechanism in a prototypical alkene-based first-generation rotary motor. We show that the initially excited bright state undergoes an ultrafast relaxation to multiple excited-state minima separated by low energy barriers and reveal a slow picosecond-timescale decay to the ground state, which only occurs from a largely twisted dark excited-state minimum, far from any conical-intersection point. Additionally, we attribute the origin of the high yields of forward photoisomerization in our investigated motor to the favorable topography of the ground-state potential energy surface, which is controlled by the conformation of the central cyclopentene rings.

Introduction

One of the most challenging tasks for the progress of mankind is the construction of nanometer-sized devices, generally called molecular machines, capable of performing specific functions in a controlled manner.^[1–3] Inspired by nature's motor proteins, scientists have developed the first artificial prototypes of molecular machines, such as molecular shuttles, scissors, and valves, which can be exploited for applications in the fields of material science, catalysis, and biomedicine. Key components of these artificial nanoscale machines are molecular motors, which are molecules or molecular assemblies converting the supplied energy into mechanical motion.^[4–8]

Among the most promising molecular motors are the so-called light-driven molecular rotary motors, which convert light energy into unidirectional intramolecular rotational motion. The earliest light-driven rotary motors are the chiral overcrowded alkenes introduced by the Nobel laureate Feringa and co-workers.^[5,9–11] The chemical structure of such motors generally consists of two moieties connected by a double bond (Figure 1a). Typically, one or both halves of the motor possess a stereogenic center, and the steric interactions around the

double bond force the molecule to assume a helical, twisted shape. This combination of two distinct stereochemical elements (i.e. helicity and stereocenter) governs the unidirectional 360° rotation of one moiety with respect to other, which is achieved through four consecutive steps (Figure 1b): two energetically uphill light-driven reactions, called cis-trans photoisomerizations (steps 1 and 3), and two energetically downhill thermal helix inversions (steps 2 and 4).

The first generation of Feringa's alkene motors include two stereogenic centers, one on each half of the molecule (Figure 1a), and is characterized by high quantum yields of forward photoisomerization (up to 99%) and a favourable position of the photostationary state.^[12–14] However, the rate of rotation of first-generation alkene motors is limited by the relatively high activation barrier for the thermal helix inversions (the rate-determining steps for rotation). This limitation motivated the development of the second class of overcrowded alkene motors, later coined the second-generation molecular motors, in which one half of the motor is replaced by an extended aromatic group (e.g. fluorene) and only one stereogenic center is required for the unidirectional rotation. Second-generation motors show enhanced rates of rotation^[15] and are more suitable for practical applications,^[6] but exhibit lower quantum yields of forward photoisomerization (not exceeding 20%) and less favourable positions of the photostationary state,^[16] compared to the first-generation motors. These drawbacks limit the efficiency of second-generation motors, since most of the absorbed light energy is dissipated as heat, especially under broadband photo-excitation.

A promising strategy to overcome the limitations of existing alkene-based motors, and to develop more efficient rotary

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Figure 1. **a** Molecular structure of the Feringa's overcrowded alkene-based first-generation motor **1** investigated in this work, with the definition of the most important geometrical coordinates. **b** Photocycle of unidirectional rotation for motor **1**, comprising two cis-trans photoisomerizations of the central double bond (steps 1 and 3), and two thermal helix inversions (steps 2 and 4).

motors, is to combine the favourable photochemical properties of the first-generation motors with the high rotation rates of the second-generation motors. However, the implementation of this strategy requires a detailed understanding of the mode of operation of both, first- and second-generation alkene motors. While the intrinsic operation details of thermal steps of the rotation cycle are now rather well known, the light-driven isomerization reactions of alkene-based motors are not yet fully understood.

In order to elucidate the photochemical behaviour of alkene-based motors, a series of time-resolved spectroscopy studies have been recently reported.^[12–14,16–24] Although these spectroscopic investigations have provided important insights into the light-induced dynamics of alkene rotary motors, a definitive explanation of the experimental observations has been mainly prevented by the paucity of computational studies on the most spectroscopically investigated motors.^[25,26] In fact, so far most of the reported computational studies on light-driven rotary motors investigated smaller-sized molecules,^[27–38] some of them theoretically designed,^[27,28,30–33,35] and the earlier computational investigations on Feringa's alkene-based rotary motors focused on compounds for which very few spectroscopic data are available.^[39–47] In addition, most of these theoretical studies focused on Feringa's second-generation motors,^[25,26,39–43,47] while only few of them investigated the photoisomerization reactions of the more efficient first-generation motors.^[44–46]

Herein, we focus on a prototypical first-generation alkene-based rotary motor (compound **1** in Figure 1a), for which the excited-state dynamics was recently investigated by time-resolved spectroscopy.^[12–14,17,24] In these spectroscopic investigations it was found that the initially excited bright state decays rapidly to another weaker-emissive bright state that converts on the picosecond timescale to a dark state, which finally relaxes back to the ground state. At variance with typical chromophores undergoing cis-trans photoisomerization, the excited state lifetime of **1** turned out to be of several tens of picoseconds,^[12,23] an effect which was attributed to the presence of an energy barrier along the photorelaxation pathway.^[13] In addition, motor **1** showed high quantum yields of forward photoisomerization (i.e. **1c**→**1tm** and **1t**→**1cm**, Figure 1b), while the reported yields for the reverse reactions are low, making the motor primed for efficient unidirectional rotary motion.^[12–14] However, at the current stage of research, an unequivocal explanation for the highly efficient photochemical behaviour of motor **1** is still missing. Understanding the light-induced dynamics in **1** is of paramount importance because the acquired knowledge can be employed to design novel rotary motors with optimal photochemical properties.

In this work, we present a complete computational characterization of the photochemical behaviour of motor **1**, considering excitation of all four ground state isomers of **1** (Figure 1b). In particular, we performed quantum chemical calculations of the low-lying electronic potential energy surfaces (PESs) of **1**

using DFT-based electronic structure methods, backed by ab initio multireference calculations. Next, we simulated the non-adiabatic excited-state dynamics of **1** using a semiempirical reparametrized technique, and the trajectory surface hopping method.^[48,49] Such a quantum-classical computational strategy allowed us to achieve a detailed understanding of the excited-state dynamics of **1**, including a clear interpretation of the reported spectroscopic findings, and to identify the origin of the high yields of forward photoisomerization in our investigated motor.

Methods

Quantum Chemical Calculations

The ground-state (S_0) minimum-energy geometries of the four isomers of motor **1** were optimized at the DFT level, using the B3LYP functional^[50,51] and the cc-pVDZ basis set.^[52] Hessian calculations were carried out to check if the S_0 -optimized geometries were energy minima. The DFT calculations were performed using the Gaussian 16 software package (Revision C.01).^[53]

The vertical excitation energies and transition dipoles for the S_1 and S_2 states of **1** were computed at the B3LYP-optimized S_0 geometries with the mixed-reference spin-flip time-dependent DFT (MRSF-TDDFT) method,^[54,55] using the CAM-B3LYP functional.^[56] MRSF-TDDFT is a recently-developed electronic structure technique which adopts one-electron spin-flip (SF) excitations from a mixed triplet reference to eliminate the spin contamination issue of single reference SF-TDDFT, thus enabling the unambiguous identification of the response states as proper singlets or triplets.^[54] At variance with TDDFT, MRSF-TDDFT is able to provide the correct topology of S_1/S_0 conical intersections and to describe excited states with significant double excitation character.^[57,58]

To benchmark the MRSF-TDDFT method for our investigated motor, the vertical excitation energies of S_1 and S_2 were also computed using the quasi-degenerate n -electron valence second-order perturbation theory (QD-NEVPT2). Additionally, to assess the accuracy of MRSF-TDDFT at geometries far from the Franck-Condon regions, QD-NEVPT2 calculations were performed for the largely twisted S_1 minima and minimum-energy conical intersections between the S_1 and S_0 states of **1**, optimized at the MRSF-TDDFT level (see below), as well as for interpolated paths between those geometries. These QD-NEVPT2 calculations are presented in Section S1 in the Supporting Information (SI).

Our choice of using the B3LYP-optimized S_0 geometries for the calculation of the vertical excitation energies was also tested by comparison with the results obtained using geometries optimized at the CAM-B3LYP level (Table S4). The protocol using the B3LYP geometries was then selected because of the better agreement with the spectroscopic data available (see section Ground-state minimum-energy structures and vertical excitation).

To investigate the topography of the PESs of motor **1**, we performed a series of constrained geometry optimizations on the S_1 PES at the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP level, in each of which the torsional angle around the central C=C bond (θ , Figure 1a) was set to a fixed value and all the other internal coordinates were relaxed. The starting coordinates for the constrained geometry optimizations on the S_1 PES were obtained by geodesic interpolation^[59] between the DFT/B3LYP optimized geometries of the ground-state isomers of **1**. In addition to performing QD-NEVPT2 calculations for selected minimum-energy geometries (Section S1), the accuracy of the CAM-B3LYP functional for the geometry optimizations in the S_1 state was tested by comparison with results computed using the BHHLYP functional, which was employed in previous works on different molecular rotary motors and photoswitches.^[43,46,60] Our calculations suggest that the accuracy of the two functionals, i.e. CAM-B3LYP and BHHLYP, is very similar for our investigated motor (see Figure S3 and Table S5).

The minimum-energy geometries in the S_1 state of motor **1** were computed by performing unconstrained geometry optimizations at the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP level, starting from the approximate minima obtained from the relaxed scans along θ . Additionally, conical intersections (Coln) between the S_1 and S_0 states of motor **1** were optimized with the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method, using an algorithm based on a sequential penalty constrained optimization that does not require the calculation of nonadiabatic couplings.^[61]

All MRSF-TDDFT calculations were carried out using the cc-pVDZ basis set^[52] and the GAMESS program package (July 31, 2022 R1 Public Release Version).^[62] For Coln optimizations, the GAMESS package was interfaced with the CIOpt program.^[61]

Nonadiabatic Excited-State Dynamics Simulations

In the nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics simulations, the electronic states of motor **1** were computed using the semiempirical configuration interaction method FOMO-CI (floating occupation molecular orbitals-configuration interaction).^[49,63,64] The semiempirical FOMO-CI scheme has proven suitable to simulate the photodynamics in a variety of large- and medium-size molecular systems.^[65–72] In the present work, we used the AM1 form of the semiempirical Hamiltonian,^[73] with parameters specifically optimized for motor **1**. Moreover, in the FOMO-CI calculations we employed an active space of 4 electrons in 7 molecular orbitals of π type, a Gaussian energy width for floating occupation of 0.10 Hartree, and a determinant space including all possible excitations within the orbital active space.

As described in Section S3, our reparametrized semiempirical method, from now on referred to as R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7), is able to satisfactorily reproduce the relative energies of the S_0 - S_2 states, the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition dipole, and selected geometrical coordinates of **1** for (i) all four ground-state isomers, (ii) the $1c \rightarrow 1tm$ and $1t \rightarrow 1cm$ relaxed scans in the S_1 state, and (iii) the optimized S_1/S_0 Coln geometries, computed with the DFT/B3LYP and MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP methods (Table S7, and Figures S5–S6). More specifically, the S_1

and S_0 energy profiles, the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition dipole, and the ground-state and Con geometries of motor **1** are well reproduced by our reparametrized semiempirical method (Figures S5–S6), while larger deviations between the R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7) results and the reference data can be identified in the β and β' angles along the relaxed scans in the S_1 state (Figure S6e–f). However, for both the $1c \rightarrow 1tm$ and $1t \rightarrow 1cm$ paths, the abrupt changes of β and β' , associated with the conformational inversion of both halves of the motor, are qualitatively well-described by our reparametrized semiempirical method. The use of the semiempirical R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7) method allowed us to greatly reduce the computational cost of our dynamics simulations and reach simulation times of several tens of picoseconds (see below).

The nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics of **1** was simulated using the mixed quantum-classical fewest switches surface hopping (SH) method,^[48] in which the quantum wavepacket dynamics is approximated using an ensemble of independent semiclassical trajectories. The starting conditions (i.e. nuclear coordinates and velocities, and the initial electronic state) for the SH simulations were sampled from ground-state thermal trajectories at 300 K that we performed with the van Gunsteren–Berendsen thermostat^[74] based on Langevin's equation. In particular, we sampled the last 15 ps of four equilibrations (one for each isomer of **1**) propagated for 30 ps. More details on the ground state equilibrations are provided in the SI (Section S4). In the sampling procedure, the initial electronic state was selected according to the radiative transition probability from the ground state,^[64] within an excitation energy range of 3.72 ± 0.15 eV for **1c**, 3.44 ± 0.15 eV for **1tm**, 3.80 ± 0.15 eV for **1t**, and 3.39 ± 0.15 eV for **1cm**. For each isomer, the selected energy window includes most of the main band of the UV/visible absorption spectrum computed along the thermal equilibration (Figure S15 in the SI).

In the SH simulations, the time evolution of the electronic wavefunction was computed by making use of a locally diabatic representation,^[49] and with a time step of 0.2 fs, employed in the integration of both the nuclear and electronic degrees of freedom. Quantum decoherence effects along the SH trajectories were taken into account using the overlap decoherence correction (ODC) scheme, with the following parameters: $\sigma = 1.0$ a.u. (Gaussian width) and $S_{min} = 5 \times 10^{-3}$ (minimum overlap).^[75,76] The rescaling of the nuclear velocities after a hop was performed in the direction of the nonadiabatic coupling vector for backward hops (lower to upper state), while the direction of the nuclear momentum was used for forward hops (upper to lower state). More details about the SH algorithm employed in the nonadiabatic dynamics simulations presented in this work, including how the transition probability between electronic states is computed, are provided in Section S5 in the SI.

For each isomer of **1**, more than 100 SH trajectories were computed, all of which starting from the S_1 state: 114 trajectories for **1c**, 115 for **1tm**, 113 for **1t**, and 110 for **1cm**. Each SH trajectory was propagated for 100 ps, with energy-conserving conditions. The three lowest singlet states (S_0 – S_2) were included in the nonadiabatic SH dynamics and, for each

simulation time, the population of each electronic state i was computed as the fraction of SH trajectories running on the i -th PES. Time-resolved fluorescence emission intensity along the SH trajectories was computed as described in Section S6 in the SI. The SH simulations were only performed in gas phase, mainly because of the experimental evidence that the photoisomerization dynamics and quantum yields of motor **1** are only weakly affected by the solvent polarity.^[13,14] Nevertheless, as explained in Section Discussion and Comparison with Experiments, our gas-phase simulations allow not only to understand in detail the intrinsic photochemical behaviour of our investigated motor, but also to propose an explanation for the experimentally observed weak effects of the solvent polarity on its excited-state dynamics and photoisomerization yields.

All the dynamics simulations were performed using the MOPAC-PI program,^[77] a development version of the MOPAC code in which the semiempirical FOMO-CI technique and the SH method were implemented. All graphics were performed using the Matplotlib package.^[78] The kdeplot function of the Seaborn library^[79] was employed to make all distribution plots, using the default smoothing parameters.

Results

Ground-State Minimum-Energy Structures and Vertical Excitation

The minimum-energy geometries of the four ground-state isomers of **1**, optimized at the DFT/B3LYP level, are shown in Figure 2, in which the most important geometrical parameters (defined in Figure 1a) are also reported.

In both stable forms, **1c** and **1t**, the central C=C bond (r) is shorter by about 0.01 Å compared to the corresponding metastable conformers **1cm** and **1tm**. Due to the steric repulsion between the two halves of the motor, in all ground-state isomers the dihedral angle θ , which quantifies the twisting around the central C=C axle, deviates significantly from the planar value of 0° (or 360°) for **1c** and **1cm**, and 180° for **1t** and **1tm**.

Important geometrical parameters of light-driven rotary motors are the pyramidalizations of the carbon atoms connected by the central C=C bond, which we quantify with the two dihedrals φ and φ' (Figure 1a). From Figure 2 one can see that for both cis isomers, **1c** and **1cm**, and the trans metastable form, **1tm**, φ and φ' only slightly deviate from 0° (no pyramidalization), while in the trans stable form **1t** the pyramidalizations of C_1 and C_1' are slightly more pronounced.

By further comparing the structures of the ground-state isomers of **1**, it is possible to notice that in both cis-trans conversions, $1c \rightarrow 1tm$ and $1t \rightarrow 1cm$, the 5-membered ring of each cyclopenta[α]naphthal-enylidene half of the motor undergoes a conformational inversion. As it can be seen from Figure 2, the β and β' dihedrals change from positive to negative values, in going from **1c** to **1tm**, and from **1t** to **1cm**. As a result, while in the **1c** and **1t** structures the two methyl groups of the stereocenters are in the axial positions, in the

Figure 2. Molecular structures of the minimum-energy ground-state isomers of motor 1, computed at the DFT/B3LYP level, with selected geometrical parameters (defined in Figure 1a). Atomic distances are reported in Å, and angles are in degrees. For each isomer, only the carbon atoms are shown and two different views are provided.

1tm and **1cm** metastable geometries both methyls assume the equatorial orientations (Figure 2). Therefore, in motor 1, the photochemical steps of the rotation cycle involve not only the cis-trans isomerization of the central C=C bond, but also a conformational change in both halves of the motor.

For the four ground-state isomers of 1, we computed the vertical excitation energies of the two low-lying singlet excited states (S_1 and S_2) using the MRSF-TDDFT method. The obtained excitation energies are reported in Table 1, in which we also provide the corresponding transition dipoles from the ground

state and the most important electronic configurations in the S_1 and S_2 states.

For all isomers of motor 1, the lowest singlet excited state, S_1 , is optically bright (i.e. its transition dipole from S_0 is large) and the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ vertical transition mainly corresponds to an excitation of one electron from the HOMO π -bonding to the LUMO π -antibonding orbital of the central C=C bond (Figure S10). On the other hand, the second lowest singlet excited state, S_2 , of 1 is essentially dark and is dominated by the HOMO \rightarrow LUMO + 1 single-electron excitation, with an additional large

Table 1. Vertical excitation energies (eV), transition dipoles (modulus in Debye, D) and main electronic configurations for the S_1 and S_2 states of the four ground-state isomers of motor 1, computed with the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method at the DFT/B3LYP optimized geometries. Only the electronic configurations with a weight larger than 0.10 are reported. In the definition of the electronic configurations, we used H to indicate HOMO and L to indicate LUMO.

Structure	State	Energy (eV)	Trans. Dipole (D)	Configuration	Weight
1c	S_1	3.65	7.906	$H \rightarrow L$	0.922
	S_2	4.21	0.312	$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.742
				$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.194
1tm	S_1	3.46	9.139	$H \rightarrow L$	0.909
	S_2	4.09	0.300	$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.768
				$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.131
1t	S_1	3.84	8.817	$H \rightarrow L$	0.920
	S_2	4.40	1.446	$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.877
1cm	S_1	3.37	7.782	$H \rightarrow L$	0.912
	S_2	3.95	0.436	$H \rightarrow L + 1$	0.704
				$H - 1 \rightarrow L$	0.191

contribution from the HOMO-1→LUMO singly-excited configuration.

For **1c**, the MRSF-TDDFT vertical excitation energy of S_1 is 3.65 eV, a value which is close to both, the energy computed at the QD-NEVPT2 level (3.56 eV, Table S2), and the spectroscopic value of ~3.5 eV (355 nm), corresponding to the maximum of the absorption band in ethanol and undecane.^[17,13] We note in passing that the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP vertical excitation energies reported in Table 1 are computed using geometries optimized at the DFT/B3LYP level, rather than using the CAM-B3LYP functional. This choice is justified by a better agreement with the spectroscopic data available: for the **1c** isomer, the S_1 vertical excitation energy computed at the DFT/B3LYP optimized geometry (3.65 eV, Table 1) is closer to the experimental value of 3.5 eV,^[13,17] compared to the energy obtained using the geometry optimized at the DFT/CAM-B3LYP level (3.75 eV, Table S4).

For the metastable isomers, **1tm** and **1cm**, the MRSF-TDDFT vertical excitation energy of S_1 is red-shifted, compared to **1c**, by about 0.2 and 0.3 eV, respectively (Table 1), while it is blue-shifted by ~0.2 eV for the stable isomer **1t**, in agreement with the QD-NEVPT2 calculations (Table S2). Moreover, both, the MRSF-TDDFT and QD-NEVPT2 methods predict that the S_2 dark state is energetically well separated from S_1 , and the MRSF-TDDFT S_2 - S_1 energy gap is about 0.6 eV at all ground-state minima of **1** (Table 1).

Potential Energy Profiles and Photorelaxation Pathways

To investigate the topography of the PESs of motor **1**, as well as the possible photorelaxation pathways, we computed the potential energy profiles of the three lowest singlet states (S_0 - S_2) for the relaxed scan along the torsion of the central C=C bond (θ) in the S_1 state, using the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method. The obtained potential energy curves are presented in Figure 3, in which we also show the transition dipole moments of the S_1 and S_2 states, selected geometrical parameters of **1**, and the partial charge of the lower half of the motor in the S_0 - S_2 states. The latter was obtained by summing the Mulliken atomic charges of the lower half of **1**, computed using the S_0 - S_2 electron densities. In Figure 3a-b, we also report the positions of the S_1 minima, which were obtained by unconstrained geometry optimizations, starting from the approximate minima obtained from the relaxed scans along θ .

For the **1c**→**1tm** pathway (Figure 3a), the S_1 potential energy profile along θ is characterized by three minima, S_1 -min₁₋₃, with θ values of 38°, 82° and 146° (Figure 3a), and S_1 energies of 3.28 eV, 3.21 eV and 3.23, relative to the **1c** S_0 minimum, respectively. S_1 -min₁ is geometrically closer to the **1c** Franck-Condon (FC) point, while S_1 -min₃ is located near the **1tm** FC geometry. For both, the S_1 -min₁ and the S_1 -min₃ geometries, the S_1 state is emissive (large S_1 → S_0 transition dipole, Figure 3c) and its energy separation from S_0 is large (~2.5 eV). The pathways connecting S_1 -min₁ and S_1 -min₃ to S_1 -min₂ on the S_1 PES are characterized by small energy barriers of 0.07 eV (6.9 kJ/mol) for the S_1 -min→ S_1 -min₂ path and 0.05 eV (5.2 kJ/mol) for S_1 -min₃→ S_1 -min₂, at the MRSF-TDDFT level, with

transition state geometries located at θ values of ~60° and ~110°, respectively. In both cases, the energy barrier crossing leads to a PES region in which the S_1 is dark (i.e. nonfluorescent, S_1 → S_0 transition dipole moment ≈0, Figure 3c) and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap is much smaller (~1.2 eV), as indicated by both the MRSF-TDDFT and QD-NEVPT2 calculations (Table S3).

Along the pathway from S_1 -min₁ to S_1 -min₂, the crossing of the barrier is followed by a significant elongation of the central C=C bond (r), accompanied by the conformational inversion of both halves of motor **1**, with β and β' changing from positive to negative values (Figure 3g). Moreover, the access to the dark S_1 PES region leads to a symmetry breaking of the molecular geometry of **1**, with a more pronounced pyramidalization at $C_{1'}$ than at C_1 ($\varphi' > \varphi$, Figure 3g). This symmetry breaking around the 90°-twisted geometry goes along with a charge separation between the two halves of the motor. In particular, in the S_1 state a partial negative charge flows from the lower half to the upper, more pyramidalized, half of **1** (Figure 3e), leading to a “sudden polarization” of the motor. At the same twisted geometries, the S_2 state polarizes by the same amount as S_1 but in the opposite direction (the lower half acquires a partial negative charge, Figure 3e), while no polarization occurs in the S_0 state. The equivalence of the two halves of **1** suggests the presence of an additional dark S_1 minimum, equivalent to S_1 -min₂ but with a larger pyramidalization at C_1 ($\varphi > \varphi'$), rather than at $C_{1'}$, and a polarization of the motor in the opposite direction, as compared to S_1 -min₂.

At molecular geometries around S_1 -min₂, the S_0 energy profile along θ is sloped towards the **1tm** minimum. This is true not only along the relaxed scan in the S_1 state (Figure 3a) but also when S_0 is optimized (Figure S11a), since the two S_0 energy profiles are essentially parallel. Thus, these results indicate that, if the S_1 → S_0 internal conversion occurs at geometries close to S_1 -min₂, the formation of **1tm** is favored.

The potential energy profiles for the **1t**→**1cm** pathway (Figure 3b) are qualitatively similar to those obtained for the **1c**→**1tm** scan. The S_1 energy curve exhibits three minima, S_1 -min₄₋₆, at θ values of 171°, 267° and 305°, respectively. S_1 -min₄ is higher in energy than the other two minima (by about 0.3 eV), but the pathway toward S_1 -min is essentially barrierless. Instead, a small energy barrier of 0.06 eV (6.0 kJ/mol) separates S_1 -min₆ from S_1 -min₅ (Figure 3b). Along the pathways connecting S_1 -min₄ and S_1 -min₆ to S_1 -min₅, the S_0 → S_1 dipole rapidly decreases to almost zero and, at the ~270°-twisted geometries, the S_1 state becomes dark (Figure 3d). At the same geometries around S_1 -min₅, the S_1 - S_0 energy gap (~1.3-1.4 eV) is significantly smaller compared to the corresponding gap at both S_1 -min₄ and S_1 -min₆ (>2.0 eV).

Similarly to **1c**→**1tm**, in the **1t**→**1cm** path the access to the dark S_1 region around S_1 -min₅ is accompanied by (i) the conformational change of the two halves of **1** (β and β' change abruptly from positive to negative values, Figure 3h), (ii) the symmetry breaking of **1**, which undergoes a larger pyramidalization on one half ($\varphi' > \varphi$, Figure 3h), and (iii) the “sudden polarization” of the motor in both the S_1 and S_2 states (Figure 3f). Moreover, at twisted geometries close to S_1 -min₅, the S_0 PES features a downhill slope towards the **1cm** isomer (Figures 3b and S11b).

Figure 3. Relaxed scans along the torsion around the central C=C bond (θ) on the S_1 state for motor 1, computed using the MRSF-TDDFT/CAM-B3LYP method. Left panels refer to the $1c \rightarrow 1tm$ scan, while right panels to $1t \rightarrow 1cm$. The grey insets highlight the regions of largely twisted and polarized geometries. **a-b** Potential energies (eV) of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states, and S_1 - S_0 energy gap. All energies are reported relative to the $1c$ S_0 minimum. **c-d** Transition dipole moments (modulus in Debye) from S_0 to the S_1 and S_2 states. **e-f** Partial charge (a.u.) of the lower half of **1** in the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states. **e-f** Partial charge (a.u.) of the lower half of **1** in the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states. **g-h** Selected geometrical parameters of motor **1** (defined in Figure 1a).

As shown in Figure 3g-h, starting from the stable isomers **1c** and **1t**, the conformational inversion of both halves of **1** (β and β' changing from positive to negative values) occurs before

reaching the largely twisted minima S_1 -min₂ and S_1 -min₅. Thus, at geometries around S_1 -min₂ and S_1 -min₅, where the S_0 PES is sloped towards **1tm** and **1cm**, β and β' assume values which

are closer to the metastable isomers **1tm** and **1cm**, than the stable forms **1c** and **1t**. This suggests that the conformation of both halves of the motor (β and β' dihedrals) significantly affects the S_0 PES topography around S_1 -min₂ and S_1 -min₅ and contribute to determining the favorable downhill slopes towards **1t** and **1cm** (Figure 3a-b).

The energy profiles in Figure 3a-b indicate that the S_1 - S_0 energy gap is quite large (>1.0 eV) throughout the **1c**→**1tm** and **1t**→**1cm** paths in the S_1 state. As predicted by both the MRSF-TDDFT and QD-NEVPT2 methods (Table S3), even at largely twisted geometries, around S_1 -min₂ and S_1 -min₅, the S_1 and S_0 states are far from being degenerate. To investigate the role of Colns in the photorelaxation of motor **1**, we searched for the minimum-energy Colns between the S_1 and S_0 states, starting from a set of twisted geometries close to S_1 -min₂ and S_1 -min₅. We found two S_1/S_0 Colns, one closer to S_1 -min₂ (Coln₁), while the other more closely related to the S_1 -min₅ geometry (Coln₂). As shown in Figure S12, both Coln₁ and Coln₂ geometries feature a significant twisting around the C=C axle ($\theta = 48^\circ$ and 213° for Coln₁ and Coln₂, respectively) and a large pyramidalization at only one of the carbon atoms of the central C=C bond, namely C_{1'}, on the upper half of **1** (Figure S12). Specifically, while φ' for Coln₁ and Coln₂ is respectively equal to 23° and 29° , φ is close to zero for both Coln geometries. Taking as reference the **1c** S_0 minimum, the energies of Coln₁ and Coln₂ are 3.85 eV and 3.59 eV, respectively. Therefore, both Coln₁ and Coln₂ lie energetically above the largely twisted energy minima S_1 -min₂ and S_1 -min₅ (located at 3.21 eV and 3.23 eV, Table S8), with Coln₁-min₂ and Coln₂-min₅ energy differences of 0.64 eV and 0.36 eV predicted at the MRSF-TDDFT level, respectively, which agree well with the corresponding values computed with the QD-NEVPT2 method, namely 0.51 eV and 0.45 eV (Table S3 and Figure S2). While Coln₁ is also energetically above the S_1 state at the **1c** and **1tm** FC geometries (with energy differences of ~ 0.2 eV), Coln₂ is located below the S_1 energy at both **1t** and **1cm** S_0 minima (Table S8). However, interpolated paths between Coln₁/Coln₂ and the FC geometries of **1**, as well as all S_1 minima, indicate the presence of high energy barriers in the S_1 state (Figures S13 and S14). These results suggest that, after excitation to the lowest bright S_1 state, Coln₁ and Coln₂ are not easily accessible.

Nonadiabatic Excited-State Dynamics

To investigate the photorelaxation and isomerization dynamics in motor **1**, we performed nonadiabatic excited-state dynamics simulations for all four isomers, using the trajectory surface hopping (SH) method and a reparametrized semiempirical electronic structure technique, as described in sec:methods-NAMD. For each isomer of **1**, a separate set of SH trajectories was computed, with starting molecular geometries sampled from the corresponding ground-state distribution.

For all isomers of **1**, the whole set of SH trajectories started from S_1 , which is the lowest bright state at the FC points (Table 1). Figure 4 shows the population dynamics for the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states of motor **1**, as obtained from the SH simulations. As it can be seen, in all isomers of **1** the main relaxation mechanism is the S_1 → S_0 internal conversion, which is completed in ~ 100 ps after the photoexcitation. Although included in the simulations, the upper-lying S_2 state is hardly populated along the dynamics. The decay of the S_1 population is well fit by a single-exponential function for all isomers of **1** (Figure 4, dashed black line) and the extracted time constants (τ_{S_1}) are 53.0 ps for **1c**, 38.1 ps for **1t**, 21.1 ps for **1tm**, and 21.8 ps for **1cm** (Table 2).

To facilitate the comparison of our simulations with the spectroscopic measurements,^[13,17] we computed along the SH trajectories running on the S_1 state the S_1 → S_0 transition dipole and energy, from which we obtained, using Eq. S14 in the SI, the time-resolved fluorescence emission intensity reported in Figure 5. As it can be observed, the time-resolved emission is characterized by an initial ultrafast decay, which precedes a weaker, longer-lived emission accompanied by an oscillation in the fluorescence profile. For all isomers of **1**, the fluorescence emission decay is well fit by a double-exponential function (dashed black line in Figure 5) with a faster decay time (τ_{f1}) of a few hundred femtoseconds, and a slower relaxation time (τ_{f2}) of a few tens of picoseconds (Table 2). The initial emission decay is significantly slower for **1t** ($\tau_{f1} \simeq 850$ fs) than the other three isomers ($\tau_{f1} \simeq 100$ – 125 fs), while the decay of the weaker, longer-lived emission is faster for **1t** and **1cm** compared to **1c** and **1tm**. For all isomers, the faster decay component (τ_{f1}) is associated with a larger relative weight (~ 70 – 90%) with respect to the slower one.

In Figure 5, we also reported the time evolution of the C=C torsional dihedral θ , averaged over all trajectories running on the S_1 state. As it can be seen, in the first ~ 1 – 2 ps of the

Table 2. S_1 state lifetime (τ_{S_1}) and time constants of the fluorescence decay (τ_{f1} and τ_{f2}) for the four isomers of motor **1**, as obtained from the surface hopping simulations. τ_{S_1} was determined by fitting the S_1 population with a single-exponential function. τ_{f1} and τ_{f2} were obtained from the fit of the time-resolved integrated fluorescence decay using a double-exponential function, and their relative weights (in parentheses) and average value (τ_f^{avg}) are also reported.

Isomer	Time constants			
	τ_{S_1}	τ_{f1}	τ_{f2}	τ_f^{avg}
1c	53.0 ps	121 fs (67%)	58.8 ps (33%)	19.3 ps
1tm	38.1 ps	126 fs (81%)	53.2 ps (19%)	17.4 ps
1t	21.1 ps	849 fs (89%)	28.9 ps (11%)	10.0 ps
1cm	21.8 ps	97 fs (75%)	26.9 ps (25%)	6.7 ps

Figure 4. Populations of the S_0 , S_1 and S_2 states for the four isomers of motor **1**, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations. In each panel, the single-exponential fitting function for the S_1 population is also shown (dashed black line).

simulations θ undergoes a large variation towards values corresponding to more twisted geometries, compared to the initial values (Time=0). For all isomers of **1**, this important change in θ takes place in the same time interval of the initial fast decay of the fluorescence emission, indicating that the relaxation of the initially excited bright state mainly occurs along θ . At longer times, θ undergoes low-frequency fluctuations that roughly match the oscillations in the slower fluorescence profile. This suggests that the oscillatory profile of the weaker emission is generated by the oscillations of θ , which originate after the initial ultrafast fluorescence decay and are damped in ~ 6 – 8 ps (Figure 5).

To analyse in more detail the molecular geometries of **1** visited during the SH simulations, in Figures 6 and 7 (panels a–b) we report the distributions of θ at different times: at the starting time (Time=0), when the trajectories are running on S_1 (S_1 active), and at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries. In Figures 6 and 7 (panels c–f), we also show the distributions of the S_1 – S_0 energy gap and the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition dipole at different times of

the dynamics. At the initial geometries (Time=0), the distributions of θ are centered at values corresponding to the minimum-energy ground-state structures of **1** (Figure 2). When the motor starts visiting the S_1 PES, it undergoes a significant twisting along θ , which shifts towards values corresponding to the S_1 minimum-energy structures that we introduced in Section Potential Energy Profiles and Photorelaxation Pathways (min_{1-6} , Figure 3a–b).

For the SH simulations where **1c** is excited, the distribution of θ for S_1 active features two separate peaks (Figure 6a), one centered at around 40° , corresponding to the S_1 - min_1 structure, and a second band spanning a broader range of θ values between 75° and 150° , which comprises both the S_1 - min_2 and S_1 - min_3 geometries. When **1tm** is excited, the motor mainly visits geometries around S_1 - min_3 ($\theta \sim 130$ – 150°) and, for a shorter time, structures close to S_1 - min_2 ($\theta \sim 75$ – 100°), as indicated by the θ distribution for S_1 active in Figure 6b. As indicated by the time evolution of the θ distribution in the S_1 state (Figure S17), the split of the S_1 population between the different excited-

Figure 5. Time-resolved fluorescence emission intensity for the four isomers of motor **1**, as obtained in the nonadiabatic surface hopping simulations. The double-exponential fitting function is also reported (black dashed line). The time-resolved fluorescence emission for the whole simulation time interval (0–100 ps) is provided in the SI (Figure S16). In each panel, the inset shows the time evolution of the C=C torsional dihedral (θ , in degree) averaged over all trajectories running on the S_1 state.

state minima occurs within the first ~ 1 – 1.5 ps after the excitation.

In both simulations following **1c** and **1tm** excitation, the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition takes place after the relaxation towards the largely twisted minimum S_1 -min₂. In fact, most of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops occur at geometries with θ values between 65° and 125° (Figure 6a–b). These hopping geometries are associated with much smaller S_1 - S_0 energy gaps (< 1.6 eV) and largely reduced $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition dipoles (< 5.0 D), compared to the starting geometries (Figures 6c–d and S20a–b). We identify these hopping structures as those corresponding to the dark S_1 PES region around S_1 -min₂, which is visited after barrier crossing from the bright minima S_1 -min₁ and S_1 -min₃ (Figure 3a). As shown in Figure S20c–d, at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops the motor exhibits a significant charge polarization, i.e. each half of the motor acquires a partial charge, which is much larger than at the starting geometries. We attribute this “sudden polarization” to the asymmetric motor geometry at $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops, as indicated by

the distribution of the dihedral difference $\varphi - \varphi'$ in Figure S20e–f.

To further analyse the geometrical changes of the motor during the dynamics, in Figure S22 we report the distributions of the β and β' dihedrals for the starting geometries (Time = 0) and those of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops. We recall that β and β' are indicative of the conformation of the two halves of **1**. As shown in Figure S22a–b, in the simulations of **1c** excitation β and β' are positive at the starting geometries, but their distributions are largely shifted towards smaller values at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries, most of them associated with negative β and β' . This indicates that in most of the SH trajectories starting from **1c** the conformational inversion of the two halves of the motor precedes the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition. On the other hand, in the simulations where **1tm** is excited, the shift of the β and β' is much smaller, compared to **1c**, and most the SH trajectories decay to S_1 retaining the initial conformations of the two halves, i.e. with negative β and β' (Figure S22c–d). These findings are consistent with the results reported in Figure 3, showing that

Figure 6. Distributions of the C=C torsional dihedral (θ , in degree) and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap (in eV) for the starting geometries (Time=0), those visited in the S_1 state (S_1 active), and the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations for isomers **1c** (panels **a**, **c**) and **1tm** (panels **b**, **d**) of motor **1**. In panels **a** and **b**, the θ values of the S_1 minima (min_{1-3} , grey color), computed at the semiempirical R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7) level, and the sub-distributions of $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries corresponding to reactive and unreactive trajectories (black and green colors, respectively) are also shown.

the region around S_1 - min_2 , where most of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops occur, is associated with negative β and β' and therefore with a conformational geometry of the two halves of the motor closer to **1tm**, rather than **1c**.

In the earlier computational investigations on second-generation motors, a key role in the photorelaxation dynamics was attributed to the pyramidalization of the carbon atoms of the central C=C bond.^[39,40,25] Therefore, we analysed the pyramidalization angles φ and φ' along our dynamics simulations and in Figure S23 we report their distributions at the starting time (Time=0) and at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops. As can be observed, the distributions of φ and φ' are generally broader at the the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops, compared to the starting time, but, similarly to the starting geometries, for most of the hopping geometries the pyramidalization angles are very small (φ and $\varphi' < 5^\circ$, Figure S23), indicating that the pyramidalization at the central axle is only slightly involved in the photodynamics of motor **1**.

After the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion, the swarm of SH trajectories is split between the **1c** and **1tm** ground-state minima. To compute the quantum yields of photoisomerization, we divided the SH trajectories for each isomer into reactive and unreactive: the trajectories starting with the excitation of a given isomer and visiting the ground-state minimum of the other isomer at the end of the simulation (Time=100 ps) are called reactive, while the other unreactive (Figure S19). From the fractions of

reactive trajectories for the simulations with excitation of **1c** and **1tm**, we obtained the following photoisomerization quantum yields (%): 85.1 ± 3.3 for **1c** \rightarrow **1tm** and 9.6 ± 2.7 for **1tm** \rightarrow **1c**, which agree well with the experimental data (Table 3).

The computed photoisomerization yields indicate that most of the SH trajectories starting from **1c** are reactive, while the majority of trajectories with excitation of **1tm** are unreactive. In both cases, most of the SH trajectories relax to the **1tm** ground-state minimum. The small fraction of trajectories which

Table 3. Quantum yields (%) for the four photoisomerization reactions of motor **1**, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations (Theoretical, this work) and in the reported spectroscopic studies (Experimental). For each quantum yield obtained in the simulations (Theoretical, this work), the reported standard deviation was computed using the binomial formula $\sqrt{\Phi(1-\Phi)}/N_T$, where Φ is the yield and N_T is the total number of surface hopping trajectories.

Reaction	Quantum yield (%)	
	Theoretical (this work)	Experimental
1c \rightarrow 1tm	85.1 ± 3.3	85 ± 10 , ^[12] 68-54 ^[14] 69 ± 6 , ^[13] 59 ± 6 ^[13]
1tm \rightarrow 1c	9.6 ± 2.7	8 ^[12]
1t \rightarrow 1cm	85.8 ± 3.3	85 ± 3 ^[12]
1cm \rightarrow 1t	6.4 ± 2.3	15 ± 3 ^[12]

Figure 7. Distributions of the C=C torsional dihedral (θ , in degree) and the S_1 - S_0 energy gap (in eV) for the starting geometries (Time = 0), those visited in the S_1 state (S_1 active), and the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries, as obtained in the surface hopping simulations for isomers **1t** (panels a, c) and **1cm** (panels b, d) of motor **1**. In panels a and b, the θ values of the S_1 minima (min_{4-6} , grey color), computed at the semiempirical R-AM1/FOMO-CASCI(4,7) level, and the sub-distributions of $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries corresponding to reactive and unreactive trajectories (black and green colors, respectively) are also shown.

decay to the **1c** minimum is characterized by $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries with θ between 65° and 90° (see the unreactive and reactive sub-distributions for the **1c** and **1tm** simulations, respectively, in Figure 6a-b), a range which is significantly narrower and shifted towards the **1c** isomer, compared to the trajectories which decay to the **1tm** minimum (θ between 65° and 125° , Figure 6a-b). However, even for this narrow range of θ values (i.e. 65° - 90°) most of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops are associated with trajectories relaxing to the **1tm** ground-state minimum (Figure 6a-b). We attribute the large selectivity for **1tm** formation mainly to the topography of the S_0 PES in the region where the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion takes place. In fact, at largely twisted geometries (θ between 65° and 125°), where most of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops occur, the S_0 PES exhibits a downhill slope towards the **1tm** isomer (Figures 3a and S11a).

When **1t** is excited, the motor rapidly relaxes to the shallow minimum S_1 - min_4 , from which it reaches, through an almost barrierless path, the lower energy S_1 PES regions around S_1 - min_5 and S_1 - min_6 (θ in the range of 225° - 325° , see the distribution for S_1 active in Figure 7a and its time evolution in Figure S18). The latter S_1 PES regions are also visited after excitation of **1cm** (Figure 7b). In this case, the trajectories relax from the **1cm** FC point to S_1 - min_6 , where they are trapped for a longer time, and subsequently reach S_1 - min_5 , after crossing the energy barrier. In both simulations starting from **1t** and **1cm**, most of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ occurs at largely twisted geometries around S_1 - min_5 (θ between

225° and 290° , see Figure 7a-b). As shown in Figures 7c-d and S21a-b, these $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries are characterized by smaller S_1 - S_0 energy gaps (< 1.6 eV) and significantly reduced $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ dipoles (< 4.0 D), with respect to the FC starting geometries. Similarly to the simulations for **1c** and **1tm**, we identify the essentially dark S_1 region of largely twisted geometries around S_1 - min_5 (Figure 3b) as the region where most of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hops take place. At these $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries the motor largely polarizes (Figure S21c-f) and the conformation of both its halves is most of the time closer to that of **1cm** (negative β and β' , Figure S22e-h).

In both simulations with excitation of **1t** and **1cm**, after the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion, most of the SH trajectories evolve to form the **1cm** isomer. The computed photoisomerization quantum yields (%) are 85.8 ± 3.3 for **1t** \rightarrow **1cm** and 6.4 ± 2.3 for **1cm** \rightarrow **1t**, in good agreement with the experimental yields (Table 3). Similarly to the simulations starting from **1c** and **1tm**, we believe that, after **1t** and **1cm** excitations, the large preference for **1cm** formation is mainly due to the shape of the S_0 PES at the geometries (around S_1 - min_5) where the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion occurs, featuring a sloped topography towards **1cm** (Figures 3b and S11b).

Discussion and Comparison with Experiments

Our quantum chemical calculations show that S_1 is the lowest optically bright state for all four ground-state isomers of **1**, while S_2 is dark and well separated in energy from S_1 . At the S_0 minima, the S_1 state is of $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ character and mainly involves a single-electron excitation from the HOMO π -bonding to the LUMO π -antibonding orbital of the central C=C bond of the motor. Relaxed scans along the C=C torsional dihedral θ on the S_1 PES reveal the presence of multiple S_1 minima along the isomerization coordinate. The computed energy barriers between these minima are low and associated with activation energies of 5–6 kJ/mol, which are close to the reported experimental value of 3.4 ± 0.5 kJ/mol for the **1c** \rightarrow **1tm** photoisomerization barrier in nonpolar solvents.^[13] For each of the four isomers of **1**, our calculations suggest that, along the pathway towards the other stereoisomer, at least two excited-state minima are visited, one of which is optically bright while the other is essentially dark. The latter minimum is associated with a larger twisting along θ and a smaller S_1 - S_0 energy gap, compared to the bright minimum. Our calculations also indicate that the energy difference between S_1 and S_0 remains quite large (> 1.0 eV) along the isomerization paths on the S_1 state, even at largely twisted geometries around the dark S_1 minimum. Additionally, the computed minimum-energy Con geometries of **1** turned out to lie significantly higher in energy (by 0.4–0.6 eV) than the optimized S_1 minima, suggesting that these degeneracy points are hardly accessible.

Our nonadiabatic dynamics simulations confirm the spectroscopic evidence that the FC region is depopulated in a few hundred femtoseconds,^[13,17] as indicated by the initially very fast decay of the computed time-resolved fluorescence emission. Our calculations also show that, during the FC bright state decay, the main structural change is a partial twisting of the C=C central bond of the motor towards the other stereoisomer. The initial FC state decays to both the bright and dark S_1 minima along the isomerization coordinate θ . In particular, the S_1 population partitions between these two minima and the sub-population of the bright minimum gives rise to a weaker emission which decays in a few tens of picoseconds, in agreement with experiments.^[13,17] This weaker fluorescence features an oscillatory profile which is generated by the oscillations of the CC torsional dihedral θ between the bright and dark S_1 PES regions. The decay of the longer-lived weak emission can be attributed to the relaxation of the bright S_1 sub-population towards the dark S_1 minimum, which mainly involves a further torsion along θ . In fact, according to our simulations, the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ radiationless transition takes place exclusively from the S_1 PES region around the dark minimum, associated with largely twisted geometries, consistent with the spectroscopic evidence that the ground state is formed by conversion from a dark excited state.^[12,14]

Our simulations also show that the energy gap at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition geometries is quite large, namely in the range of 1.0–1.5 eV, for all isomers of **1**. Notably, the S_1/S_0 minimum-energy Con geometries are significantly higher in energy than the lowest S_1 minima and, therefore, are never accessed during the

dynamics. This finding is at variance with what was proposed in the spectroscopic studies of **1**, in which it was suggested that the motor decays to the ground state through a Con point.^[12,17,13,14] Moreover, the fact that in motor **1** no Con point is involved in the internal conversion to the ground state significantly distinguishes the photorelaxation dynamics of **1** from that of the previously investigated overcrowded alkene motors. In particular, in the earlier computational investigations of Feringa's second-generation alkene motors the reported mechanisms of excited-state decay involve S_1/S_0 Con geometries,^[39,40,25] suggesting that Cons play a dominant role in the photoisomerization dynamics of overcrowded alkene motors. Our results indicate that this is not the case for **1** and the absence of accessible S_1/S_0 Cons is a peculiar feature of our investigated motor.

Another important difference between our calculations and the earlier reported simulations of overcrowded alkene motors is about the involvement of the pyramidalization at the central C=C bond in the photodynamics. Our simulations indicated that only a moderate change in the pyramidalization angles occurs during the excited-state dynamics of motor **1** and most of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries are associated with a very small pyramidalization. Instead, in the reported computational investigations of Feringa's alkene motors it was shown that the pyramidalization coordinate plays a very important role in the excited-state dynamics of second-generation motors, as it represents the main relaxation coordinate towards the accessible S_1/S_0 Con points of those motors.^[25,39,40] Therefore, following the classification of rotational motions in light-driven molecular motors,^[42,36] our investigated motor **1** undergoes photoisomerization mainly through an axial motion, rather than a precessional rotation, which is instead the preferred motion in second-generation fluorene motors.^[42]

At the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ hopping geometries, motor **1** exhibits a strong charge separation between the two halves. This effect, called "sudden polarization", was noted in earlier studies of cis-trans photoisomerization of nearly symmetric ethylenic molecules such as **1**.^[80–83] In the case of **1**, the sudden polarization at largely twisted geometries can explain the spectroscopic observation that the excited-state lifetime of the motor is reduced by increasing the solvent polarity.^[13,14] In fact, a more polar medium can induce stabilization of the twisted polarized S_1 state, relative to the unpolarized S_0 , and therefore an acceleration of the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ decay. Additionally, the fact that the charge separation develops in the S_1 dark region after the barrier crossing, rather than in the bright S_1 minima, is consistent with the experimental evidence that the emission spectrum of **1** is only weakly affected by solvent polarity.^[13]

The excited-state lifetime, τ_{S_1} , obtained in our dynamics simulations is of several tens of picoseconds for all four isomers of **1**, namely 53 ps for **1c**, 38 ps for **1tm**, and 21 ps for **1t** and **1cm** (Table 2). Such a slow $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ relaxation dynamics is consistent with the most recent spectroscopic studies for **1**.^[12,14] Taking as reference the decay time of the longer-lived spectroscopic dark state in nonpolar solvent, the experimental excited-state lifetimes are: 71 ps for **1c**, 40 ps for **1tm**, and 13 ps for both **1t** and **1cm**.^[12] Our simulations well reproduce

these decay times, as well as their relative order (Table 2). In addition, our dynamics simulations allow to understand the origin for the slow $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ decay of **1**, which can be attributed to two effects: (i) the energy barriers along the photorelaxation paths, which trap the motor in the bright S_1 minima for several picoseconds, and (ii) the relatively large S_1 - S_0 energy gap throughout the S_1 PES region visited during the dynamics, including the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition geometries.

According to our simulations, the split of population between the stable and metastable ground-state isomers takes place after the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ conversion, which occurs at largely twisted geometries essentially halfway between the two ground-state isomers. Therefore, it is the shape of the S_0 PES that mainly determines the partition between the two stereoisomers. This finding may also explain the weak dependence of the $1c \rightarrow 1tm$ isomerization yield on solvent polarity observed in experiments,^[13,14] as S_0 does not polarize along the isomerization coordinate (Figure 3e) and its PES is expected to be only weakly affected by medium polarity. For the forward reactions $1c \rightarrow 1tm$ and $1t \rightarrow 1cm$, the photoisomerization yields obtained in our dynamics simulations are high and equal to 85%, in very good agreement with experiments^[12,13,14] (Table 3). The computed yields for the reverse reactions are much lower, namely 10% for $1tm \rightarrow 1c$ and 6% for $1cm \rightarrow 1t$, in line with the experimental findings^[12] (Table 3). Thus, our simulations support the experimental evidence that motor **1** is primed for efficient unidirectional photoisomerization. Moreover, in addition to confirming the experimental findings, our calculations indicate that the high selectivity for one stereoisomer is mainly due to the optimal topography of the S_0 PES in the region where the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition takes place, which is characterized by a downhill slope towards the preferred isomer.

Our simulations also show that each photoisomerization of **1** involves not only the cis-trans conversion of the central C=C bond, but also the conformational inversion of the two halves of the motor, with the two methyls of the stereocenters moving from the axial to the equatorial orientations, or vice versa. This conformational change of each half plays an important role in determining the S_0 PES topography at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition and, therefore, the photoisomerization yields of **1**. In fact, in the simulations with excitation of the stable isomers **1c** and **1t**, associated with high photoisomerization yields, the conformational inversion of the two halves occurs most often in the excited state before the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition takes place. On the other hand, when **1tm** and **1cm** are excited, most of the SH trajectories decay to S_0 conserving the initial conformation in each half of the motor and the resulting photoisomerization yields are low. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study reporting that a conformational inversion of the central rings can control the photoisomerization efficiency of overcrowded alkene motors.

Conclusions

We have investigated the photochemical behaviour of a prototypical alkene-based first-generation rotary motor, using a

combination of quantum chemical calculations and surface hopping nonadiabatic dynamics simulations. In our computational study, we analysed the photorelaxation mechanisms following excitation of all four ground-state isomers of the motor.

Our quantum chemical calculations indicated that S_1 is the lowest optically bright state for all four isomers of the motor. Moreover, the computed minimum-energy paths along the central C=C torsional dihedral revealed the presence of multiple S_1 minima separated by low energy barriers, in agreement with the experimental findings. The identified S_1 minima have distinct spectroscopic features: the minima closer to the FC points are bright, although with an emission rate considerably reduced with respect to the FC zone, while those associated with largely twisted geometries are dark. The latter minima are also characterized by a reduced S_1 - S_1 energy gap and a significant charge polarization between the two halves of the motor.

Our nonadiabatic dynamics simulations allowed to fully characterize the photorelaxation and isomerization mechanisms in the investigated motor. Specifically, we showed that the initially excited bright state undergoes an ultrafast geometrical relaxation, involving a partial twisting along the central C=C bond, consistent with the time-resolved fluorescent measurements. This ultrafast relaxation is followed by the splitting of the S_1 population between the multiple S_1 minima and the subpopulation of the bright minimum gives rise to a weaker longer-lived emission, as observed in the experiments, providing a clear interpretation of the spectroscopic data. Moreover, our simulations indicated that the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ decay only occurs at largely twisted geometries around the dark S_1 minimum, consistent with the spectroscopic observation that a dark excited state is populated before the relaxation to the ground state. At the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition geometries, around the dark S_1 minimum, our calculations indicated that the S_1 - S_0 energy gap is quite large (about 1 eV). Therefore, at variance with what was proposed in the spectroscopic studies of our investigated motor, we showed that the internal conversion to the ground state does not involve Coln geometries. This finding makes the photorelaxation dynamics of our studied motor significantly different from that of the early investigated second-generation motors, for which it was reported that Colns play a key role in the photoisomerization dynamics.

Our simulations also showed that the partition of the population between the ground-state isomers occurs after the $S_1 \rightarrow S_1$ conversion and the photoisomerization yields of the motor, well reproduced by our simulations, are mainly determined by the topography of the S_0 PES in the region where the excited-state decay occurs. Specifically, the high yields of forward photoisomerization can be attributed to a favorable slope of the S_0 energy profile along the isomerization coordinate at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transition geometries. In addition, we showed that the conformation of each half of the motor plays an important role in determining the shape of the S_0 PES at the $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ transitions and, therefore, the photoisomerization yields of the motor.

Overall, our study reveals the excited-state dynamics and photoisomerization mechanisms of a prototypical first-generation rotary motor and provides a detailed explanation of the spectroscopic observations, thereby contributing to the development of general rules connecting the chemical structure of a motor with its photochemical behaviour. Additionally, the highly efficient and unidirectional photoisomerization mechanism revealed by our simulations can be used as a novel target to design light-driven rotary motors with improved photochemical properties. In particular, our results suggest that a promising strategy to improve the photochemical behaviour of light-driven rotary motors might be to reduce the accessibility of Colns to the ground state and optimize the topography of the ground-state PES in the larger-gap region where the excited-state decay takes place.

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Conflict of Interests

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13350539>, reference number 13350539.

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